

Bottom-Up Fabrication of Nanostructured Bicontinuous and Hexagonal Ion-Conducting Polymer Membranes

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Abstract

We report a simple photo-crosslinking process to chemically arrest the different liquid-crystalline structures formed by self-assembly of wedge-shaped amphiphilic mesogens. Using this route, we obtained free-standing polymer membranes with columnar or bicontinuous cubic structures, depending primarily on the relative humidity conditions during UV-induced crosslinking. These crosslinked mesostructures show much higher thermal stability in comparison with that of the liquid-crystalline structures of the initial monomers. The ionic conductivity of the membranes strongly depends on the water uptake preceding the polymerization reaction. According to NMR diffusometry, which can quantify water transport in one or two environments in these materials, the water diffusion rate in the membrane with bicontinuous cubic structures can approach values of commercial ion conducting membranes. These studies show promise for use of this fabrication route in practical applications for selective ion and water transport.

Introduction

Recently, there has been growing interest in the development of synthetic functional membranes for a wide range of practical applications. Ion exchange membranes can be used in water treatment (purification and softening), biotechnology, electro dialysis, electrolysis, soil technology, energy conversion (fuel cells and redox flow batteries) and myriad other applications.¹⁻⁶ The targeted properties of such membranes strongly depend on the final use, but the usual requirements are controlled molecular transport (conductivity, water flux), chemical and thermal stability, and robust mechanical properties at different levels of water uptake. Since its commercialization in the late 1960s by Du Pont, the perfluorosulfonate copolymer Nafion® has become the benchmark material due to its outstanding performance. At present, the majority of the commercially available membranes are based on similar materials.^{7,8} The high proton conductivity, outstanding mechanical and thermal stability, chemical robustness and high selectivity to small cations allow Nafion® membranes to be used in many fields. Interestingly, these materials have found numerous applications, which are even different from the originally targeted permselective separator in chlorine-alkali electrolyzers, and can now be employed in fuel cells, electrochemical devices, sensors, batteries, or as ion-exchange membranes. It is however worth mentioning that Nafion presents some drawbacks such as elevated production costs, use of fluorinated materials, as well as MeOH permeability, which is too high for use in direct methanol fuel cells (DMFC) without modifications. These deficiencies provide motivation in the search for alternatives to Nafion membranes.

A cheaper and greener alternative to Nafion and its derivatives is the use of non-fluorinated ionomers.⁸⁻¹⁰ Poly(arylene ether) materials such as poly(arylene ether ether ketone) (PEEK) or poly(arylene ether sulfone) are often preferred, [cf. refs. 11-12] based on cost and stability considerations. The introduction of ionic, or active, sites can be done by direct copolymerization with sulfonated monomers or by electrophilic sulfonation of the polymers. The hydration behaviour and the ionic transport of the membranes will depend on the degree of sulfonation in this case.¹² To avoid the loss of mechanical stability of these membranes upon water uptake it is necessary to limit the concentration of active sites in the ionomer or to covalently crosslink the polymer chains. In the latter case, the membranes can retain their dimensional stability at high temperatures (~90°C) and in the swollen state, their main disadvantage being that under dry conditions they exhibit brittleness, making handling difficult. Apart from the polymers bearing sulfonate

groups such as polysulfones¹³ or sulfonated poly(imide)s,¹⁴ there are also other alternatives to Nafion such as composites based on polybenzimidazoles and inorganic acids such as H₃PO₄¹⁵ or polymers bearing other ionic groups such as phosphonic acid.¹⁶ Independent of the system, the concentration and distribution of ionic groups play a fundamental role in the membrane performance. The topology of the aqueous domains controls the local current densities, which means that there exists a direct relationship between the ionomer structure and ionic conductivity^{17,18} Control over nanostructure is thus a key target for improving membrane performance.¹⁹

Molecular self-assembly through non-covalent interactions to form supramolecular structures has shown to be a promising route toward new functional materials.²⁰⁻²⁵ Intermolecular forces involved in these processes can determine the supramolecular architecture formed by molecular aggregates. For instance, self-organization of complexes formed by polymer chains and low-molecular-weight compounds tend to form microphase-separated morphologies of lamellar phase (Lam).²⁶ In the past, the possibility of obtaining ion-conducting channels through self-assembly of tapered-shaped mesogens was shown by Ungar and co-authors.²⁷ In this case, the ionic receptors were forming the central channel, while the flexible aliphatic side chains – the continuum matrix. The DC conductivity of the compound was found to dramatically increase at the crystal-columnar phase transition proving that the channels of high internal mobility obtained through the self-assembly process were indeed responsible for the conductive properties of the material. The use of polymerizable wedge-shaped molecules was recently shown for fabrication of polymeric thin films with physically continuous and vertically-aligned small (i.e., 1-nm-diameter) pores.²⁸

In our previous research, we demonstrated that wedge-shaped sulfonate amphiphiles self-assemble into supramolecular columns whereby the sulfonate groups are stacked close to the columnar axis, forming an ion channel with a well-defined geometry.^{29,30} In order to optimize the ion-conducting properties of the membranes based on such structures, alignment of the mesophases is required.³¹ Nevertheless, this alignment can be made unnecessary by using structures based on cubic bicontinuous (Cub_{bi}) phases,³² which are formed by a labyrinthic 3D structure composed of two non-intersecting chiral networks of channels. Regardless of the mesophase structure, in order to suit real life applications the supramolecular arrangement needs to be covalently connected to form a polymer matrix and yield self-standing films. Photopolymerization has shown to be an effective method to do so.³³⁻³⁶

Previously, we explored humidity-induced phase transitions in a novel wedge-shaped sulfonate as well as the possibility to perform photopolymerization of the liquid-crystalline phases to fabricate mechanically-stable nanoporous membranes with a tailored ion-channel structure for possible applications in separation and catalysis.^{37,38,42} In this case, the ion channel size and topology can be controlled through swelling of the system in vapors of water⁴³ or other solvents.⁴⁵

In the present paper, we describe the fabrication and properties of self-assembled membranes polymerized under different conditions. In particular, the thermal stability and swelling capacity of the different mesophases are a strong function of the relative humidity. We also focus on the effect of the initiator concentration on the final mesostructure arrested during polymerization. Finally, in order to correlate material morphology with transport properties, we compare ion water transport properties of the membranes polymerized in columnar or cubic bicontinuous phases. We employ NMR diffusometry to quantify water transport in these materials, and couple this to conductivity measurements to assess ion transport. These studies bring new understanding to stable membranes formed from self-assembled mesophases, and show promise for use of this fabrication route in practical applications for selective ion and water transport.

Experimental

Synthesis:

Sodium 2,3,4-tris(11'-acryloylundecyl-1'-oxy)benzenesulfonate, **A-Na**, was synthesized according to the synthetic procedures reported previously.^{29,37} It is worth mentioning that the chemical structure of the mesogen was selected based on the equivalent weight of **A-Na** (ca. 900 g mol⁻¹), which is close to that of Nafion (1100 g mol⁻¹).⁷

Membranes preparation:

Figure 1 schematically shows the preparation procedure for self-standing membranes. Firstly, the photoinitiator, 2,2-dimethoxy-2-phenylacetophenone, was added at concentrations ranging from 1 to 10% w/w to solutions of **A-Na** (ca. 60 mg·ml⁻¹) in chloroform. The resulting solutions were drop-cast on glass slides ($\varnothing = 1\text{cm}$) previously cleaned with methanol in an ultrasound bath. Secondly, after solvent evaporation, the samples were left at room temperature for several hours, being protected from light, in order to allow for mesophase formation. Next, the samples were placed inside Teflon vessels together with selected salt solutions used to control the relative humidity

conditions during photopolymerization.^{38,46} A UV lamp was used simultaneously as a source of radiation and a lid for the sample preparation chamber, as shown in Figure 1. Once the chamber was sealed, samples were equilibrated for 24 hours at the desired humidity prior to UV illumination. Light exposure was then applied for 8 hours using a wavelength $\lambda = 366$ nm. Importantly, the samples were placed on massive metal plates to avoid heating of the material during UV irradiation. Once the polymerization process was completed, the films were detached from the glass support by immersion in diluted HF solutions (0.5%) and extensively rinsed with water. The obtained self-standing membranes were insoluble in chloroform after polymerization. Hereafter, the different membranes are identified as A-Na_{x-y}%, where x stands for the relative humidity and y stands for the amount of initiator used in the photopolymerization reaction.

Figure 1. Schematics showing the method of preparation of self-standing membranes.

Characterization Techniques:

Polarizing optical micrographs (POM) were obtained by using a LEITZ Laborlux 12 POL S with crossed polarizers.

Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) measurements in transmission geometry using synchrotron radiation were performed at the BM26 beamline of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble (France). The wavelength used was $\lambda = 1.03\text{\AA}$ (12 KeV). The X-ray patterns were recorded with a Pilatus 1M 2D detector.

The norm of the reciprocal space s -vector ($|s| = 2\sin\theta/\lambda$, where θ is the Bragg angle and λ is the wavelength) was calibrated using several orders of a silver behenate standard. The X-ray analysis, including background subtraction and radial integrations of the 2D patterns, was performed using home-built routines designed in the IgorPro software package (Wavemetrics Ltd.).⁴⁷ Variable-temperature SAXS measurements (see Figure 3 below) were performed after equilibration in ambient atmosphere (RH \approx 50 %, T = 25°C) and with the help of a Linkam DCS600 heating/cooling stage.

The membranes for ion conductivity measurements were annealed at 25 °C inside sealed vials for 60 h. The vials were equilibrated at different RH-values (55% and 100%) generated over saturated solutions of Mg(NO₃)₂ and deionized water, respectively. The samples were then sandwiched between two glass plates coated with indium tin oxide (ITO), and measured under the same conditions. The humidity level was monitored using a digital humidity sensor (Sensirion SHT75). Through-plane ion conductivity was measured at 25°C by AC impedance spectroscopy using an Electrochemical Work-station IM6 (Zahner-Elektrik GmbH&Co. KG, Germany). The spectra were recorded using amplitude of 1V in the frequency range from 10⁰ to 10⁸ Hz. The conductivity values were obtained by fitting the impedance spectra using a model containing a serial connection of a parallel and a serial RC-circuit.

For water diffusion measurements, two crosslinked membranes A-Na_{55-1%} and A-Na_{100-3%} were held on a vacuum line at 1 mTorr for 24 hours, and then placed in RH-equilibration tubes above Mg(NO₃)₂ solution and pure H₂O at room temperature for \geq 1 day to reach RH = 55% and RH = 100%, respectively. Immediately prior to NMR measurements, the membranes were blotted using lint-free wipes to remove any surface water rapidly and thoroughly. Each membrane was then quickly placed into a capillary of 1.8 mm O.D. \times 1.5 mm I.D. and sealed to maintain water content during NMR measurements. All pulsed-field-gradient PFG NMR diffusometry measurements were obtained using a Bruker Avance III wide bore 400 MHz (9.4 T) NMR equipped with a Diff60 diffusion probe and a 2 mm ¹H solenoid coil providing a 90° RF pulse length of 1.0 μ s. The pulsed-gradient stimulated echo (PGSTE) sequence was used to measure diffusion, with an effective gradient pulse length of $\delta = 2$ ms (actual pulse length of the sinusoidal pulse was 3.2 ms), a 2 ms gradient stabilization time after each gradient pulse, a gradient pulse spacing of $\Delta = 50$ ms, and gradient strengths varying from $g = 20$ G/cm to $g = 1600$ G/cm. 16 to 24 gradient steps were applied, and the number of scans varied

from 64 to 256 to yield sufficient signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Diffusion was measured along the z-direction (spectrometer magnetic field direction). The self-diffusion coefficient D was obtained by fitting the measured signal intensity I as a function of gradient strength g using the Stejskal-Tanner equation: ⁴⁸

$$I = I_0 e^{-D\gamma^2 g^2 \delta^2 (\Delta - \delta/3)} = I_0 e^{-Db} \quad (1)$$

Where γ is the gyromagnetic ratio of the nucleus observed and $b = \gamma^2 g^2 \delta^2 (\Delta - \delta/3)$ the Stejskal-Tanner factor. All PFG NMR diffusometry experiments were conducted at 25°C. Errors in D are $\leq \pm 10\%$ due to fitting of two diffusing components in some cases and measurement of slow diffusion in others.

Results:

The photopolymerization process, as described in the experimental section, results in self-standing membranes with thicknesses ranging from 50 to 70 microns. Depending on the initial amount of initiator, the optical and mechanical properties of the membranes vary significantly. For a low initiator content (1% w/w), the membranes are transparent and flexible, while the ones prepared with 10% of initiator are translucent and more brittle. Figure 2 shows polarized optical micrographs (POM) corresponding to the self-standing films obtained by photopolymerization of the **A-Na** mesophase under different conditions. It can be seen that birefringent textures are observed for the membranes polymerized at low humidity, independent of the amount of initiator employed. By contrast, when the polymerization is accomplished at high RH conditions, the initial concentration of the acetophenone derivative seems to have some influence on the final structure, as judged from the optical textures. In the case of the membranes prepared at RH = 100%, for low concentrations of initiator (1-3% w/w) some birefringence is still detected. However, polarized micrographs obtained on the membranes with higher initiator content appear completely black. This signifies fully isotropic phases, for example, cubic phases.

Figure 2. POM images of the self-standing membranes polymerized under different RH conditions (RH = 55% - top; 100% - bottom) using different concentrations of the initiator. The insets show macro-images of the membranes in reflected light.

The microstructure and phase behavior of the membranes were further studied by in-situ X-ray scattering during swelling and heating experiments. Figure 3 shows the evolution of the 1D-reduced intensity as a function of temperature during heating ramps carried out from 25°C to 200°C at 5°C/min.

Figure 3. 1D-reduced X-ray diffractograms measured during heating experiments conducted on the membranes after equilibration in ambient atmosphere ($RH \approx 50\%$, $T = 25^\circ\text{C}$). The Miller indices of the main reflections are indicated. Insets show 2D X-ray patterns corresponding to the initial state of the samples.

The positions of the reflections in each case allows identification of the corresponding mesophases. In the case of a $A\text{-Na}_{55-1\%}$ membrane, the ratio of the corresponding d -spacings was found to be $1:\sqrt{3}:2$, confirming the presence of a 2D Col_{hd} lattice, which is in agreement with our previous work.³⁷ Under ambient humidity conditions ($RH = 40\text{-}50\%$), the unit cell parameter of the Col_{hd} phase was found to be 4.16 nm. All phases and their corresponding d -spacings calculated at the initial stage of the heating ramp are summarized in Table 1. Upon heating, a shift in the peaks' positions towards higher angles can be appreciated, which indicates a slight lateral shrinking of the

columnar structure. Thus, during heating, a decrease of the unit cell parameter of the Col_{hd} phase in the lateral dimension of *ca.* 3% is observed. This behavior is typical of materials with negative thermal expansion coefficients along the transverse-to-column directions and has been previously documented for supramolecular and covalent columnar mesophases (see, e.g., refs. 49-51). Decrease of the unit cell parameter of the Col_{hd} phase has been sometimes explained by softening of the aliphatic tails of the mesogens, allowing closer packing of the columns.⁵² Interestingly, the columnar structure is stable up to 200°C, well above the temperature range commonly used for applications of ion-conducting membranes. This temperature range presents a striking contrast to a non-crosslinked mesophase, the isotropization temperature of which is only of 51.2°C.³⁵

Addition of a higher amount of initiator during photopolymerization under the same RH conditions has a strong impact on the structure. The A-Na_{55-10%} membrane shows two broad peaks that can be tentatively assigned to a strongly distorted columnar phase (Fig.3, top right panel). The fact that the POM micrographs show birefringence supports this phase assignment, since a completely isotropic phase would appear black. According to the latter results, when membranes are polymerized at RH = 55%, the use of a small amount of initiator (1% in weight) is already enough to ensure the mechanical stability of the polymerized membrane, while at the same time it preserves the columnar structure of the mesophase and its swelling capability (see the text below). When using higher concentrations of acetophenone derivative, the photo-reactive molecule will not only act as initiator but could also covalently bond to the aliphatic chains after a hydrogen abstraction process,⁵³ thereby decreasing the flexibility of the tails and avoiding the formation of ordered hexagonal packing of the columns. Therefore, a higher degree of crosslinking may, on one hand, improve the mechanical stability of the membranes, but on the other hand, could reduce the rate of ion or water diffusion due to disordering of the channel structure¹.

For preparation of the membranes under RH = 100%, i.e., with a completely swollen mesophase, four different concentrations of the initiator were used. When the crosslinking agent was added at the concentration of 1% w/w, the membrane can be partially dissolved in chloroform after UV irradiation, resulting in a gel-like material with poor mechanical stability. However, even under these conditions, a self-standing membrane was obtained after removal of the non-polymerized fraction. The structural evolution of the A-Na₁₀₀ membranes with temperature is presented in Figure 3 (bottom). The Miller indices of the main reflections are assigned, according to our previous study

on highly oriented thin films.^{37,38} In all cases, a coexistence of cubic bicontinuous phases, namely gyroid (G) and diamond (D), together with lamellar (Lam) phase is observed. The crosslinking procedure gives rise to a decrease in the lattice parameters compared to the non-polymerized mesophase, a fact that is documented for other similar systems.³⁵ The lattice parameter of the cubic phases of A-Na₁₀₀ membranes decreases by about 15% with respect to the values of the pure mesophase, i.e., from 14 nm down to 12 nm. Generally, among polymerized membranes, the lattice parameter is the smallest for the highest content of the initiator (Table 1). Taking into account that the classical phase evolution with increasing water content in inverse lyotropic systems is columnar→cubic→lamellar,^{24,54} the persistence of the cubic phases at such high humidity is most likely explained by their metastability,⁵⁵ or perhaps a distorted phase behaviour due to the high ion density. As observed in different systems, the timescale for the formation of stable phases can vary significantly (from minutes to months).⁵⁶ The metastable behavior of the cubic phases in this case makes the transformation rates to become significantly longer than the photopolymerization process. In the corresponding POM micrographs (Fig. 2), it can be seen that higher initiator content correlates strongly with lower birefringence. This effect can be explained by a decrease of the fraction of lamellar phase (i.e., the only birefringent phase) present in the membranes. This trend was also confirmed by X-ray data. According to Figure 3, the initial intensity of the reflections corresponding to the lamellar phase strongly decreases for membranes prepared with higher initiator contents (6 - 10% w/w). Regarding the thermal stability of the membranes, the A-Na_{100-1%} membrane exhibits the lowest stability, as can be inferred from the fact that on heating the membrane structural peaks disappear around 170°C. The other membranes remain stable up to 200°C (Fig. 3). Interestingly, the lattice parameter of the cubic phases is unaffected by heating, as can be concluded from the constant positions of the corresponding reflections. By contrast, the microstructure of the lamellar fraction is much more sensitive to temperature. Thus, shifting of the lamellar phase peaks to higher scattering angles reflects a decrease in the lamellar d-spacing on heating from 4.3 nm down to 3.8 nm, i.e. by 15%. We note that there is a modest shift in the d-spacing ratio (1.16) of the 110D and 111D peaks for the A-Na_{100-6%} and A-Na_{100-10%} samples (Table 1) relative to the expected ratio (1.22), most likely due to a distortion that is caused by the cross linking process and arrested by the polymer covalent constraints.**[REF]** Note that for the uncrosslinked A-Na materials, we observe the d-spacing ratio 1.22.**[ADD Y Chen JPCB 2014 PAPER REF - #38 in last version]** It is conceivable that we are

observing a conversion of diamond phase to gyroid and/or other phases (e.g., including the lamellar) during crosslinking and we cannot rule out such an effect at this time. However, we believe that diamond phases are present, and we will continue to investigate such phenomena in more detail in future work on these materials.

Membrane	Phase	hkl	d_{exp} [nm]	d_{calc} [nm]	Lattice param. [nm]
A-Na ₅₅ (1%)	Col _{hd}	100	3.60	3.60	a=b=4.16
		110	2.08	2.08	
		200	1.80	1.80	
A-Na ₅₅ (10%)	unknown	-	-	-	-
A-Na ₁₀₀ (1%)	Cub _{bi}	-	5.26	-	a _G =12.88 a _D =7.43
	Lam	001 002	4.29 2.15	4.30 2.15	d ₀₀₁ =4.30
A-Na ₁₀₀ (3%)	Cub _{bi}	110 _D 211 _G	5.79 4.92	5.79 4.92	a _G =12.05 a _D =8.19
	Lam	001 002	4.26 2.13	4.26 2.13	d ₀₀₁ =4.26
A-Na ₁₀₀ (6%)	Cub _{bi}	110 _D 211 _G 111 _D	5.34 4.91 4.57	5.46 4.91 4.46	a _G =12.03 a _D =7.73
A-Na ₁₀₀ (10%)	Cub _{bi}	110 _D 211 _G 111 _D	5.23 4.81 4.48	5.35 4.91 4.37	a _G =11.78 a _D =7.57

Table 1. Experimental (d_{exp}) and calculated (d_{calc}) d-spacings and lattice parameters of the different phases present in the polymerized membranes. The measurements were conducted at RH ~ 50%. Col_{hd} stands for columnar hexagonal disordered phase, Cub_{bi} for cubic bicontinuous, Lam – for lamellar, D- for diamond, and G- for gyroid.

Importantly, the high thermal stability exhibited by the membranes does not prevent them from also exhibiting a high water swelling capacity. This is a critical feature since, similar to Nafion and other ion conducting membranes, the presence of absorbed water is a prerequisite to achieve high ionic conductivity.⁵⁷ Figure 4 shows the 1D-reduced X-ray patterns recorded on the membranes prepared under different conditions such as A-Na_{55-1%} and A-Na_{100-3%} for which Col_{hd} and Cub_{bi} phases are present. The measurements were performed before (dry state) and after (swollen state) immersion in water for 24 h at two different temperatures, i.e., 25°C (blue lines) and 80°C (red lines). Clearly, there are no qualitative changes in the X-ray patterns, except for a limited shift

of the peaks' position to lower scattering angles upon immersion in water. This shift indicates an increase of the ionic channel size upon water uptake. The unit cell parameter of the Col_{hd} phase increases by 7% with respect to the dry state (i.e., from 4.0 to 4.3nm), while the lattice parameters of the cubic phases in the $\text{A-Na}_{100-3\%}$ membrane increase by more than 10% compared to that of the dry membranes (i.e., from 11.15 and 7.52 up to 12.45nm and 8.43nm for gyroid and diamond phases, respectively). Finally, the d_{001} spacing of the lamellar phase present in the $\text{A-Na}_{100-3\%}$ membrane increases from 3.95 to 4.3nm, i.e., 8%.

During heating of the swollen membranes up to 80°C, a shift of the peak positions is observed towards higher scattering angles. This can be accounted for by the conformational change in the alkyl chains, as explained previously. Nevertheless, the lattice parameters of Col_{hd} and Cub_{bi} phases do not fully recover the values observed under dry conditions, indicating that some water is still retained inside the ion channels.

Figure 4. X-ray diffraction curves of the $\text{A-Na}_{55-1\%}$ (left) and $\text{A-Na}_{100-3\%}$ (right) under different conditions: dry (grey) at 25°C, swollen (blue), at 25°C and swollen at 80°C (red). For the dry experiments, the samples were held under vacuum for 24 h at 25°C, then sealed with wax prior to measurements. For the swelling experiments, the membranes were immersed in water for 24 h then sealed with wax prior to measurements. The Miller indices of the main reflections are indicated in each case. The dashed vertical line is a guide to the eye facilitating peak position comparison.

Figure 5. (a) Single pulse NMR spectra (black) compared with diffusion-weighted spectra of A-Na_{55-1%} (red) and A-Na_{100-3%} (blue) membranes after being immersed in water for 72 hours. The single pulse spectra include all protons in the sample (wedge molecules plus water), while the diffusion-weighted spectra only report on the mobile molecules. (b) Stejskal-Tanner plots of water protons for water diffusion in the two membranes, showing fits to obtain two diffusion coefficients and two populations corresponding to the fast and slow diffusing components. The x -axis is the Stejskal-Tanner factor in Eq. 1, $b = \gamma^2 g^2 \delta^2 (\Delta - \delta/3)$.

In order to investigate the transport properties of these membranes, we have also measured water diffusion coefficients in the membranes using pulsed-field-gradient (PFG) NMR diffusometry.^{38,48} NMR diffusometry and spectroscopy can also quantify the populations of multiple diffusing species in different material phases, and can serve more broadly to correlate morphology with transport information in macromolecular and supramolecular electrolyte systems.³⁸⁻⁴¹ For these materials, we are able to correlate transport information with phase behavior, water uptake, and morphological features.

Figure 5a shows the single pulse NMR spectra (black) compared with diffusion-weighted spectra of the A-Na_{55-1%} (red) and A-Na_{100-3%} (blue) membranes equilibrated at RH = 100%. We have focused on these membranes because they have relatively fast water transport, and thus are of most interest in terms of desirable membrane properties. The single pulse spectrum shows NMR response of all protons in the sample including the signals from crosslinked wedge molecules (broad peak) and signals from absorbed

water (sharp peak). The standard spectrum of dried membranes gives a broad peak, which includes only proton signals from wedge molecules (spectrum not shown), the difference between the two spectra of hydrated and dried membranes yields only the water proton signal. Therefore we can obtain water uptake $\lambda(\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{SO}_3^-)$ directly from the integration ratio of water peak to the broad peak, and these measurements agree with gravimetric measurements to within errors. The diffusion-weighted spectrum only shows signals from nuclei with relaxation times long enough to survive the gradient encoding times (2×5.2 ms = 10.4 ms), when transverse relaxation (T_2) is active, and the 50 ms diffusion delay Δ , when longitudinal relaxation (T_1) is active. Since the membrane matrix is immobile (with very short T_2), we can only detect water signal (sharp peak) using these diffusion measurements. Figure 5b shows ^1H Stejskal-Tanner signal attenuation plots for absorbed water of A-Na_{55-1%} (RH 100%) and A-Na_{100-3%} (RH 100%). Each peak in the diffusion-weighted spectra in (a) is attenuated (as a function of gradient strength) to show the two components evident in (b). We can clearly quantify two diffusion components and two populations for both membranes. We furthermore can correlate water transport, water uptake (swelling) and ionic conductivity for the set of membranes that possess fast transport. Figure 6 shows results for ionic conductivity as well as water uptake and water diffusion coefficients as measured by SAXS and NMR spectroscopy and diffusometry. The water uptake (λ) values for the A-Na_{55-1%} and A-Na_{100-3%} membranes, stabilized under different relative humidity conditions (55 and 100%) are shown in figure 6a. According to peak shifts observed in the X-ray diffractograms (Fig. 4) the the unit cell parameter of the Col_{hd} phase can increase up to about 7% at RH = 100%. This increase can be correlated to a maximum water uptake of $\lambda = 7.3$ water molecules per sulfonic group (Fig. 6a), in reasonable agreement with integrations of the NMR signals in Fig. 5a ($\lambda = 5.1$). Furthermore, the capability of water absorption of the bicontinuous phases appears to be much higher. In these cubic phases, the absorption increases with the relative humidity, and for water vapor saturated atmosphere the A-Na_{100-3%} membrane absorbs 13.5 water molecules per SO_3^- group (NMR integration gives $\lambda = 13$). The water channel diameter of the different structures can then be estimated by X-ray and swelling ratio, as explained in our previous work.³⁸ The channel diameter calculated for the swollen membranes is 24.5 Å, only slightly smaller than that observed in the non-polymerized mesophase.³⁸ Despite the small contraction, this cubic phase ionic channel size increases more than 60% compared to that of the columnar phase, which was

calculated to be 15 Å. As shown below, this difference has a profound impact on ion conduction properties and water mobility.

Figure 6. (a) Water uptake, (b) through plane ionic conductivity and (c) diffusion coefficients measured at different relative humidity conditions for A-Na_{55-1%} and A-Na_{100-3%} membranes (estimated error in $D \leq 10\%$). The number inside the parentheses

(part c) indicates the population percentage of the fast diffusion component (estimated error $\leq 5\%$ of total signal).

Figure 6b shows the through-plane ionic conductivity measured on the same membrane samples, A-Na_{55-1%} and A-Na_{100-3%}, after equilibration under different RH conditions. The conductivity values of the A-Na_{55-1%} membrane, i.e., the one with columnar mesostructure, increases with RH, reaching nearly $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$. Nevertheless, the membrane with a 3D interconnected channel mesostructure shows increasing values of conductivity as water content is increased, surpassing $10^{-3} \text{ S} \cdot \text{m}^{-1}$, which is more than one order of magnitude higher. In Figure 6c, we observe a similar trend in the water diffusion coefficients. At RH = 55%, only one-component diffusion for both A-Na_{55-1%} and A-Na_{100-3%} membranes is observed. By increasing RH to 100%, a much faster (20-30 \times) diffusion component appears. Similar to our previous study on non-crosslinked mesophases,³⁸ we attribute the two diffusion components to free water diffusing inside ionic channels of liquid-crystalline regions (fast component) and water diffusing through the amorphous regions (slow component) in the crosslinked membranes. At low water content, water diffusing through ionic channels occurs at a similar rate as water diffusing through amorphous regions, due to the small size of these channels. However, when increasing humidity to 100%, water uptake increases significantly, and water diffusion is much faster due to the enlarged ionic channel size. Also consistent with conductivity measurements, water transport of A-Na_{100-3%} is faster than that of A-Na_{55-1%} at both RH = 55% and RH = 100%. In agreement with that observed for the pure mesophase, the bicontinuous cubic phases are far superior in terms of water and ion transport, especially at high water contents. Compared to the non-polymerized mesogen measured at RH = 100%, where diffusion coefficients are $D = 1.7 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (fast) and $D = 4.2 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (slow),³⁸ A-Na_{100-3%} membrane provides a factor of 10 slower diffusion coefficients $D = 1.5 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (fast) and $D = 5.3 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ (slow). This could indicate shrinking of the ionic channels and amorphous regions during crosslinking, or introduction of channel structural defects upon crosslinking. Presumably, such a defect structure can be improved by optimization of the humidification and photopolymerization process. Nevertheless, our study reveals that **A-Na** membranes crosslinked at RH of 100% display impressive water transport properties, with one (population dominant) fast component approaching that of some commercial conducting polymer membranes.

Conclusions:

We have demonstrated formation of nanostructured polymer membranes containing ionic nanochannels of different size and topology, fabricated by photopolymerization of mesophases formed by low-molecular-weight wedge-shaped amphiphiles bearing reactive groups in their alkyl periphery. Based on our previous studies of the phase behavior of the wedge-shaped mesogen in the presence of water vapor,^{36-38,42-45} we carried out a photopolymerization reaction starting from lyotropic structures of the mesogen ranging from columnar hexagonal (1D), to lamellar (2D), to bicontinuous cubic (3D) phases.

We found that at adequate concentrations of the photoinitiator, the structure of the lyotropic phase can be preserved upon photopolymerization. Formation of a chemically crosslinked network significantly enhances the thermal stability of the mesophases, and, at the same time, does not significantly reduce their swelling capacity.

The ionic conductivity of these membranes was found to be strongly dependent on the water uptake preceding the polymerisation reaction. According to NMR diffusometry measurements, the water diffusion coefficient in the membrane with bicontinuous cubic structures can approach the values typical of commercial perfluorosulfonated membranes. All of these observations demonstrate that this fabrication route, based on supramolecular self-assembly under variable humidity followed by chemical crosslinking, shows promise for practical applications.

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